

清華大學

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REactor neutrino LIquid xenon Coherent Scattering experiment

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On behalf of the RELICS Collaboration

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Coherent Elastic neutrino-Nucleus Scattering (CEvNS)

CEvNS is an SM interaction between neutrinos and matter

$$\sigma_{\text{CEvNS}} = \frac{G_F^2}{4\pi} F^2(q^2) Q_W^2 E_\nu^2$$

$$Q_W = N - Z(1 - 4\sin^2 \theta_W) \sim N$$

Cross-section is 2 orders of magnitude higher

Detectable energy is 4 orders of magnitude lower!

Observable: kinetic energy of nuclear recoil

$$\langle T \rangle = \frac{2 E_\nu^2}{3 M_A}$$

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Coherent effects of a weak neutral current

Daniel Z. Freedman†
 National Accelerator Laboratory, Batavia, Illinois 60510
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 (Received 15 October 1973; revised manuscript received 19 November 1973)

If there is a weak neutral current, then the elastic scattering process $\nu + A \rightarrow \nu + A$ should have a sharp coherent forward peak just as $e + A \rightarrow e + A$ does. Experiments to observe this peak can give important information on the isospin structure of the neutral current. The experiments are very difficult, although the estimated cross sections (about 10^{-38} cm² on carbon) are favorable. The coherent cross sections (in contrast to incoherent) are almost energy-independent. Therefore, energies as low as 100 MeV may be suitable. Quasi-coherent nuclear excitation processes $\nu + A \rightarrow \nu + A^*$ provide possible tests of the conservation of the weak neutral current. Because of strong coherent effects at very low energies, the nuclear elastic scattering process may be important in inhibiting cooling by neutrino emission in stellar collapse and neutron stars.

Global Effort in CEνNS Measurements

1974 –D. Freedman: coherent scattering of neutrinos on the whole nucleus (CEνNS)

2017 – observation by COHERENT in stopped π -beams \leftrightarrow $F(q^2)$ - not fully coherent

2024 – solar ^8B neutrinos by XENONnT and PandaX , and by LZ (2025)

2025 – CONUS+ with reactor neutrinos

Sanmen Neutrino Experiments: RELICS (Xe) + RECODE (Ge)

Mass 5-10 kg

Fiducial Mass 32 kg, 62kg LXe in total

Measurement of CEνNS with **Xe** and **Ge** elements

RELICS Concept

Advantages of LXe TPC :

- ❑ high single electron detection efficiency
- ❑ XY position reconstruction
- ❑ low threshold

low nuclear recoil energy :

- ❑ Energy ROI : $[0.3, 1] \text{ keV}_{nr}$
- ❑ S2 ROI : $[120, 240] \text{ PE}$

S2-only analysis :

- ❑ S1 signal is too weak to detect
- ❑ Further reduce the energy threshold

Low-threshold detection :

- ❑ Single PE trigger rate $> 90\%$
- ❑ **Single-Electron** detection gain $> 30 \text{ PE}$

Challenge: Backgrounds

Cosmic Ray Particles

- Cosmic μ
- Cosmic neutron
- Others...

Reactor

- Reactor Neutron
- Reactor γ
- Others...

Detector Material

- Material γ , β
- Others...

Background ratio

- cosmic ray neutron 20.1%
- muon induced neutron 0.1%
- delayed electron 78.5%
- cosmic & material 1.3%

NR background and shield design

--- Cosmic-Ray neutron

---- Reactor & Environment neutron

NR Background:

- $(7.7 \pm 0.7) \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ of $[0.3, 1] \text{ keV}_{NR}$
- Dominated by cosmic ray neutron

ER background

-- Cosmic Ray neutron

-- Material

-- Cosmic Muon

LXe intrinsic -- Rn222 -- Kr85

S2 only --- No Z position

> 95% efficiency

Fiducial Volume:

R < 12 cm

Edge backgrounds

S2 width cut:

S2 width > 0.22 μs

Liquid-gas interface backgrounds

ER Background:

$(3.10 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{day}^{-1} \cdot \text{keV}^{-1}$ average of [0,20] keV_{ER} before S2 width cut

Delayed Electron (DE) Background

Large S2 energy deposition

Delayed electron sources:

- ❑ Observed by large LXeTPCs experiments and prototype
- ❑ Emission of electron following large energy deposition
- ❑ Pile-up of single electrons distorts the physical signal

see delayed
electron poster
by Yang Lei

Delayed electron background:

- ❑ ~ 10 Hz muon flux
- ❑ Pile-up DE events rate higher than CEvNS events

DE Background Suppression

Efficiency of Selection Method

	Signal Acceptance	Background Remaining
Pattern + Correlation	~52%	~0.01%
Waveform	~80%	~10%

Pattern + Correlation selection:

- ❑ CEvNS : Closer to single - point events.
- ❑ DE: More linked to the preceding muon track.

waveform selection:

- ❑ CEvNS : Gaussian
- ❑ DE: More dispersed

Result:

- ❑ dead time cut ~ 20ms
- ❑ Several orders of magnitude reduction

Physics Potential for CEvNS

CEvNS ROI: [120, 240] PE

	Events / (32kg·year)
CEvNS	4639.7
Cosmic Ray Neutron	339.9
Muon Induced Neutron	1.7
ER	21.1
DE Pile-ups	1325.1

Delayed-electrons pile-up events will be dominant background

➤ **Improve position reconstruction**

OPEN ACCESS

Reactor neutrino liquid xenon coherent elastic scattering experiment

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Uncertainty of the weak mixing angle Caused by Q_y uncertainty

RELICS Prototype

RELICS Prototype

❖ [NST 37\(1\), 14 \(2025\)](#)

❖ [arXiv: 2511.18693, 2510.24196, 2510.04846](#)

Demonstration of Energy Threshold and DE Suppression

[arXiv: 2511.18693](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.18693)

Single electrons are detected with high efficiency
DE background can be suppressed via HE veto

RELICS-5: First Step @ Sanmen

	Events / (32kg·year)
CEvNS	4639.7
Cosmic Ray Neutron	339.9
Muon Induced Neutron	1.7
ER	21.1
DE Pile-ups	1325.1

	Events / (5 kg·year)
CEvNS	4639.7 x 0.15 ~ 720
Cosmic Ray Neutron	339.9 x3 ~ 1000
Muon Induced Neutron	1.7 x 1 ~ 2
ER	21 x 5 ~100
DE Pile-ups	1325.1 x 0.33 ~ 440

Physics Potential with RELICS-5

RELICS-5 is competitive in CEvNS sensitivity

THU USTC SUSY Westlake CUHK Beihang

- **CEvNS is an exciting topic in Neutrino Physics**
- **RELICS aims at CEvNS measurement from reactor neutrinos with a LXeTPC**
- **RELICS prototype has been built to study the feasibility**
- **RELICS-5 will start in 2026, and aims to detect CEvNS in 2027**

Thanks for your attention!

Global Effort in CEνNS Measurements

$$\sigma \propto Q_W^2 \propto (N - (1 - 4 \sin^2 \theta_W)Z)^2$$

$$\Rightarrow \sigma \propto N^2$$

SNS

Solar

Reactor

Figure: Kate Scholberg

Calibration of the RELICS prototype

❖ [NST 37\(1\), 14 \(2025\)](#)

❖ [arXiv: 2511.18693, 2510.24196, 2510.04846](#)

Physics Potential for Axion-like Particles

Dent et al., PRL 124, 211804 (2020)

Production

Primakoff Process

Compton-like Scattering

De-excitation of nucleus

Detection

Inverse Compton-like pair production Axion decay e^+e^-

pairs Inverse Primakoff

Axion decay - photon

Physics Potential for Axion-like Particles

Sensitivity :

- 20 kg-year exposure
- Search for the reactor ALPs

Sanmen Neutrino Experiments: RELICS (Xe) + RECODE (Ge)

■ Combined Search:

- Far site: RELICS Xe, RECODE Ge
- Near site: RECODE Ge

Ge: electric cooling

Near site
(~11m)

堆芯

Far site
(~22m)

Ge: LN2 cooling

RELICS Xe